

Supporting Information

**Isolation and Comparison of Root-associated Endophytic
Actinobacteria from Healthy and Diseased Soybean and
Identification of the Antifungal Compounds against
Sclerotinia sclerotiorum (Lib.) de Bary**

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Figure S1. ^1H NMR (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **1** in $\text{MeOH-}d_4$

Figure S1. ^{13}C NMR (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **1** in $\text{MeOH-}d_4$

Figure S1. ^1H NMR (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **2** in $\text{MeOH-}d_4$

Figure S1. ^{13}C NMR (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **2** in $\text{MeOH-}d_4$

Figure S1. ^1H NMR (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **3** in CDCl_3

Figure S1. ^{13}C NMR (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **3** in CDCl_3

Figure S1. ^1H NMR (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **4** in CDCl_3

Figure S1. ^{13}C NMR (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **4** in CDCl_3

Figure S1. ^1H NMR (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **5** in CDCl_3

Figure S1. ^{13}C NMR (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **5** in CDCl_3

Figure S1. ^1H NMR (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **6** in CDCl_3

Figure S1. ^{13}C NMR (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **6** in CDCl_3

Figure S1. ^1H NMR (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **8** in CDCl_3

Figure S1. ^{13}C NMR (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **8** in CDCl_3

Figure S2. ^1H NMR (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **9** in CDCl_3

Figure S2. ^{13}C NMR (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **9** in CDCl_3

Figure S2. ^1H - ^1H COSY (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **9** in CDCl_3

Figure S2. HSQC (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **9** in CDCl_3

Figure S2. HMBC (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **9** in CDCl_3

Figure S2. Roesy (600 MHz) spectrum of compound **9** in CDCl_3

Optical rotation measurement

Model : P-1020 (A060460638)

No.	Sample	Mode	Data	Monitor Blank	Temp. Cell Temp Point	Date Comment Sample Name	Light Filter Operator	Cycle Time Integ Time
No.1	5 (1/3)	Sp.Rot	-21.5380	-0.0028 0.0000	22.5 10.00 Cell	Wed Sep 12 09:59:35 2018 0.00130g/mL MeOH HSA14213	Na 589nm	2 sec 2 sec
No.2	5 (2/3)	Sp.Rot	-18.4620	-0.0024 0.0000	22.5 10.00 Cell	Wed Sep 12 09:59:40 2018 0.00130g/mL MeOH HSA14213	Na 589nm	2 sec 2 sec
No.3	5 (3/3)	Sp.Rot	-17.6920	-0.0023 0.0000	22.5 10.00 Cell	Wed Sep 12 09:59:46 2018 0.00130g/mL MeOH HSA14213	Na 589nm	2 sec 2 sec

Figure S2. Optical rotation data of compound **9** in MeOH

Figure S2. CD spectrum of compound **9** in MeOH

Figure S2. UV spectrum of compound **9** in MeOH

Sample Name: HSX14213
 KBr压片
 采集时间: 星期五 9月 14 15:06:53 2018 (GMT+08:00)
 仪器型号: NICOLET iS10
 Software version: OMNIC 9.8.372

样品扫描次数: 16
 背景扫描次数: 16
 分辨率: 4.000
 采样增益: 1.0
 动镜速度: 0.4747
 光阑: 80.00

Figure S2. IR spectrum of compound **9**

Qualitative Analysis Report

Data Filename	HSX14213.d	Sample Name	HSX14213
Sample Type	Sample	Position	P1-A2
Instrument Name	Instrument 1	User Name	
Acq Method	s.m	Acquired Time	7/25/2018 9:41:16 AM
IRM Calibration Status	Success	DA Method	Default.m
Comment			

Sample Group	Info.
Acquisition SW	6200 series TOF/6500 series
Version	Q-TOF B.05.01 (B5125.2)

User Spectra

Peak List

m/z	z	Abund	Formula	Ion
64.0159		77316.7		
274.2745	1	120462.95		
318.3008	1	135382.3		
362.327	1	63291.14		
453.1672	1	70563.11		
468.1555	1	68312.99	C22 H27 N3 O5 S	(M+Na)+
484.1501	1	117351.11		
500.1256	1	50905.09		
913.3232	1	45645.14		
922.0098	1	46406.51		

Formula Calculator Element Limits

Element	Min	Max
C	3	60
H	0	120
O	0	30
N	0	5
S	0	1

Formula Calculator Results

Formula	CalculatedMass	CalculatedMz	Mz	Diff. (mDa)	Diff. (ppm)	DBE
C22 H27 N3 O5 S	445.1671	468.1564	468.1555	0.90	1.92	11.0000

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Figure S2. HRESI spectrum of compound **9**